

Dyes derived from 2-Aminothiazole-4:5-dicarboxylic Acid.

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The object of the present communication was to prepare fluoresceins, eosines and rhodamines from 2-aminothiazole-4:5-dicarboxylic acid similar to those obtained from phthalic anhydride, quinolinic acid, succinic acid, iminazoledicarboxylic acid, itaconic and citraconic acids, with a view to compare their colour and fluorescence.

2-Aminothiazoledicarboxylic acid condenses with aromatic amino- and hydroxy-compounds directly and it has been found that the addition of condensing agents such as sulphuric acid and zinc chloride does not give better yield. The constitution of these compounds can be represented as follows, taking resorcinolaminothiazomalein as a typical representative.

Resorcinolaminothiazomalein.

The following aromatic amino- and hydroxy-compounds have been condensed with the aminothiazoledicarboxylic acid and the corresponding thiazomaleins obtained:—resorcinol, catechol, phloroglucinol, orcinol, amidophenol and *m*-dimethyl-*m*-amidophenol. The condensation product with resorcinol has been brominated and the corresponding tetrabromo-compound obtained.

Two compounds are probably formed by the condensation of 2-aminothiazoledicarboxylic acid with resorcinol, one of which is brown and the other green. The former is the true resorcinolamino-

thiazomalein which dissolves in alkali with a green fluorescence whilst the latter, which is formed only in traces, does not exhibit any fluorescence in alkaline solution. It might be a substance resembling 1:3-dihydroxyanthraquinone in constitution (*cf.* Ghosh, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 115, 1102).

As in these compounds the double bonds are in juxtaposition, it is very probable that in accordance with the theory of molecular strain, the intensity of their colour should be very similar to those of the citraconeins (Dhar and Dutt, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 4, 253), and in fact, in general properties, colour and fluorescence it appears that dyes derived from 2-aminothiazoledicarboxylic acid are similar to those of the corresponding substances obtained from citraconic acid.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The condensations of 2-aminothiazole-4:5-dicarboxylic acid with the aromatic hydroxy-and amino-compounds have been effected by direct heating of the components at temperatures varying between 170° and 200°. The results of experimental observations are summarised below :—

Name.	Appearance.	M.p.	Colour in alkali.	Colour of fluorescence.	Analysis : C, H, % in brackets.
Resorcinol	... Reddish-brown rectangles.	246°	Orange-red	Green	N, 7.91 (8.12)
Catechol	... Black-brown rectangles.	Above 298°	Pinkish-red	...	N, 7.53 (7.72)
Phloroglucinol	... Grey needles	Above 298°	Red	...	N, 7.25 (7.46)
Oreinol	... Grey powder	Above 300°	Orange-red	Green	—
m-Amidophenol	Grey rectangles.	Above 300°	Red	Faint pink	N, 11.90 (12.03)
Dimethyl-m-amido phenol	Brick-red	Above 330°	Magenta	Faint pink	N, 13.73 (13.62)
Tetrabromo-resorcinol	Brick-red	210°	Pink	Yellow-green	N, 4.19 (4.41)

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